

been made by a consideration of the polymerisation of the acid which has been corroborated by the observed values of the molecular weights of the sodium salt of the thymonucleic acid in different preparations ranging from 5×10^5 to 1×10^6 (Signor, Caspersson and Hammarsten, *Nature*, 1938, 141, 122; Tennet and Vilbrandt, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 424, 1806) and of the yeast nucleic acid of about 2×10^4 (Loring, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1939, 135, 128; *Proc. Amer. Chem. Soc. Biochem.*, 1939, 61; Kunitz, *J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1940, 24, 15). Miescher (*loc. cit.*) also noted the high molecular weight of the acid. The nucleic acids thus are substances with high molecular weight and it appears that the tetranucleotidic structure is many times present within the actual molecule. The linkage between the tetranucleotide in such molecules might well involve the fifth hydrogen atom of the tetranucleotide. Hence as more and more tetranucleotides polymerise to form the large molecule, the basicity of the latter approaches more and more to the observed value of four per tetranucleotide unit. The reverse phenomenon has been observed in the case of yeast nucleic acid which, when broken up, begins to exhibit the presence of the fifth H atom (Allen and Eiler, *loc. cit.*).

Evidently the principal physicochemical work that has been done on the nucleic acid mainly refers to the elucidation of its structure. The nucleic acid in aqueous solution behaves as an electrolytic colloid having considerable electrical conductance comparable to that of electrolytes. Hammarsten's observations (*loc. cit.*) first of all brought out that the osmotic pressure of thymonucleic acid solutions was very much less than that calculated from its electrical conductivity, although it agreed quite well with the values from freezing point measurements. Hammarsten referred this anomaly to the size of the ions into which the nucleic acid ionised; the smaller ions being lost osmotically in the sphere of attraction of ions of bigger size and of opposite sign. By using ions of comparable dimensions he could show that the anomaly disappeared and the behaviour came back to normal.

The osmotic anomaly observed by Donnan and Harris (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, 99, 1534) in the Congo-red solutions was explained by the authors as due to the non-diffusibility of bigger ions which kept the smaller ions of opposite charge bound by electrostatic attraction.

A more rational explanation was suggested by Linderstrom-Lang (*Compt. rend. trav. Lab. Carlberg*, 1926, 16, No. 16; *vide* also the discussion by McBain, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 1636) from thermodynamic grounds suggesting that some type of aggregate formation was proceeding in the system which was directly responsible for the anomaly referred to above. Van Rysselberghe (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1934, 38, 646) has discussed this aspect from the Debye-Hückel interionic attraction theory on the assumption that nucleic acid molecules polymerise to form micelles of larger dimensions. McBain and Betz (*loc. cit.*) attempted an explanation from the view-point of the existence and formation of neutral micelles above certain concentrations in these systems of colloidal electrolytes.

Thus, as evident from the above, aggregate formation has been held responsible for the high molecular weight of the acid, the occurrence of the tetrabasicity and also for the suggested structure of the acid. Formation of aggregates in aqueous solution has also been believed to be at the root of osmotic anomaly observed by Hammarsten, although different workers have looked at the problem from different angles of vision.

The works in connection with aggregate formation in solution have been carried out mostly by observing how physical properties of the solution change with its concentration and plotting the observation with concentration graphically. A break or kink in the curve has been regarded as a positive evidence (Hartley, *Kolloid Z.*, 1939, 88, 22). Any physical property can be chosen, but the two properties which have been generally used have been the specific volume (Grindley and Bury, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 679) and the equivalent conductivity, of which again the latter has been regarded as the more important (Hartley, *ibid.*, 1938, 1968; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 2347; Lottermoser and Frotacher, *Koll.-chem. Beih.*, 1937, 15, 303; Lottermoser and Püschel, *Kolloid Z.*, 1933, 63, 175; McBain and Salmon, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 42, 426; McBain, Laing and Titley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 1279).

In the study on the variation of equivalent conductivity with concentration, there is a fundamental agreement in the observations of the different workers who worked with different systems. The $\Delta - \sqrt{c}$ curve, with the help of which these observations have been generally represented, shows a sudden kink at low concentrations. The position and occurrence of this inflexion point (critical concentration) have been correlated to the number of carbon atoms in the case of long chain compounds (*cf.* Lottermoser and co-workers, *loc. cit.*). At higher concentrations the $\Delta - \sqrt{c}$ curve reaches a minimum beyond which there is a tendency to increase as the concentration becomes higher.

All the workers in this line agree that at very low concentration the colloidal electrolytes in aqueous solution remain ionised and the ions are monomeric (as opposed to aggregated micelles). At the inflexion point aggregate formation starts which proceeds up to higher concentrations. It is in point of the nature of these aggregates that divergence of opinion amongst different workers really arises. McBain (*loc. cit.*) believes that these aggregated micelles are neutral molecules, which according to Lottermoser and co-workers (*loc. cit.*) acquire surface charge by ionisation at the surface or by adsorption of ions from the solution and thus exhibit cataphoretic motion. Hartley (*loc. cit.*) believes in only one type of micelles, *viz.*, the ionic micelles which by interionic attraction build up an ionic atmosphere and keep an increasing number of counter-ions bound in this atmosphere. The increase occurring in the $\Delta - \sqrt{c}$ curve beyond the point of minimum Δ has been explained by McBain as due to the formation of ionic micelles in this region, while Hartley believes this to be due to the disruption of the ionic atmosphere whereby a number of counter-ions are released thus increasing the conductivity of the solution.

Lottermoser has, however, discussed these view-points critically (Lottermoser and Frotscher, *loc. cit.*). No final conclusions have as yet been reached.

Thus although the high molecular weights of the nucleic acids have been explained on the assumption of polymerisation or association, and although the nature of the variation of equivalent conductivity (Λ) with concentration has also found explanation on assumption of aggregate formation in aqueous solution of the acid, no attempt has been made to ascertain as to whether this aggregation is of similar nature to that occurring in the case of well known colloidal electrolytes, like salts of long chain fatty acids or of long chain sulphonic acids, etc., nor has any attempt been made to settle whether this aggregation process is sudden and starts abruptly for the critical concentration or whether it proceeds at all concentrations without showing a break anywhere in the $\Lambda - \sqrt{c}$ curve.

The object of the present investigation is to open the question again on the same lines as in the case of typical colloidal electrolytes viz. by studying the physical properties of the aqueous solution of the acid and noting how they change with concentration of the solution. For this reason a variety of physical properties has been studied and their variations noted with concentration. The nature of the $p - f(c)$ curve is expected to furnish the useful informations on these points where p is the value of any physical property at a concentration c , and $f(c)$ is any function of this concentration.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of the Sol.—Yeast nucleic acid (B. D. H.) was purified essentially by the method of Bungenberg de Jong (*Koll.-chem. Beih.*, 1938, 47, 254) by dissolving the acid (1.5g.) in the least quantity of *N*-ammonium hydroxide solution and subsequently precipitating the acid by excess of 3*N*-acetic acid. Three repetitions of the process were found essential to reduce the ash content from 1.2% to 0.08%. The residue after washing with alcohol, free from acetic acid, and drying at room temperature was tested for its purity (*cf.* Hammersten, *loc. cit.*). Chlorides, phosphates and proteins were found to be absent. Further, moisture, phosphorus, nitrogen and ash contents have been estimated, results of which are presented below. The figures represent the mean value of two determinations in the cases of moisture and the ash content, and three determinations in the cases of nitrogen and phosphorus.

TABLE I

	Sample I.	Sample II.	Sample III.
Moisture (105° for 12 hrs.)	11.08%	10.68	11.90
Phosphorus (by conversion into phosphate and precipitation by NH ₄ -molybdate)	8.70	8.58	8.80
Nitrogen (Kjeldahl's method)	14.80	14.60	14.78
Ash content (by incineration)	0.08	0.09	0.11
Nitrogen to phosphorus ratio (N/P)	1.70	1.71	1.71

Evidently the three different samples prepared by the same method yielded analytical results almost identical. The N/P ratio is almost constant in the three cases which according to Hammersten (*loc. cit.*) should be the guiding factor in the estimation of purity of samples.

Solutions were prepared by carefully weighing out 0.25 g. of the acid per 100 c.c. of conductivity water (sp. conductivity = 1.15×10^{-6} mho). Before introducing the acid the conductivity water was sterilised by prolonged boiling and cooled carefully avoiding contamination from outside. The acid was then introduced and the mixture shaken in a mechanical shaker for 3 to 4 hours when the solid acid became dispersed. The solution, when viewed under the ultramicroscope, exhibited the Tyndall phenomenon and hence was of colloidal character. On keeping the sol overnight a part of the solid settled down, the remaining part formed a fairly stable suspension and did not settle easily. The suspension which was slightly yellowish was preserved under a layer of pure toluene.

Methods of Measurement.—Present investigation has been principally confined to determination of the hydrogen-ion activity, specific conductivity of the suspension and the cataphoretic velocity of the colloidal particles at different concentrations of the suspension. Measurements were all carried out at $35^\circ \pm 0.1$ except where stated otherwise.

Potentiometric measurements were carried out with hydrogen electrode against a saturated calomel half element. Pt-electrodes for potentiometric measurements were freshly prepared every day after removing the grey deposit at the end of each day's work and a fresh deposit was formed by replatinisation. The electrode was washed free from acid by the usual method (*cf. Mukherjee et al., J. Agric. Sci., 1936, 6, 517*).

Cataphoretic velocity was measured by the microscopic method in a cell of the Freundlich and Abramson type at the room temperature. Readings were always taken at 0.21 depth of the cell. The potential gradient was measured by the help of Ohm's law from a knowledge of the current flowing through the cell and the specific conductivity of the suspension.

Concentrations of the suspension were determined by precipitating the acid with alcohol and washing the precipitate thoroughly with alcohol-water mixture. The acid so obtained was dried at room temperature (30°) and weighed. Concentration was finally calculated after making allowance for the moisture content of the specimens which were found to contain about 11% of moisture approximately.

Ageing and Reproducibility.—Four different samples of nucleic acid solutions (vide Table II) were studied to investigate into the effect of ageing so far as the specific conductivity, hydrogen-ion activity and cataphoretic velocity were concerned*.

* These properties were studied everyday as a matter of routine work. Data for all the days of observation have not been presented in the table for economy of space. Those for 1st, 5th, 10th, 15th and 20th days have been shown.

TABLE II

No. of day.	Sample I (conc. 1g./litre)			Sample II (conc. 1g./litre)		
	Sp. condy.	pH.	C.V.	Sp. condy.	pH.	C.V.
1	6.01×10^{-4}	3.00	5.62×10^{-4}	6.12×10^{-4}	2.96	5.22×10^{-4}
5	6.00	3.01	5.62	6.10	2.98	5.25
10	6.03	3.00	5.60	6.13	2.94	5.15
15	6.05	3.02	5.50	6.09	2.90	5.20
20	6.15	3.10	6.21	6.25	3.15	7.20
25	6.50	3.23	—	6.98	3.29	—
	Sample III (conc. 1.08g./litre)			Sample IV (conc. 0.098g./litre)		
1	6.09	2.97	5.18	6.00	3.02	5.06
5	6.10	2.95	5.11	6.05	3.00	5.07
10	6.07	2.92	5.10	6.02	2.99	5.01
15	6.08	2.96	5.20	6.02	3.01	5.01
20	6.21	3.10	5.90	6.20	3.25	5.93
25	6.40	3.27	—	6.32	3.40	—

It is also clear from the table that for the first 15 days there was no indication of any change in the properties studied after which they were found to undergo change with the progress of time. After about a month's time growth of moulds could be detected inside the sol. For this reason no experiments were done in this investigation and in all subsequent work with any suspension preserved for more than a fortnight.

Different samples of nucleic acid suspensions were used in course of these experiments since the same suspension could not be used 15 days after its preparation. It was therefore thought necessary to ascertain whether different samples of the nucleic acid sol could have comparable properties. From Table II again it is evident that the reproducibility in four different samples is fairly satisfactory so far as pH, specific conductivity and cataphoretic speeds are concerned provided the concentrations are equal.

Attainment of Equilibrium.—In potentiometric and conductometric titrations (recorded in this investigation) bases were always added at intervals of 15 to 20 minutes. Attainment of necessary equilibrium within this short time has been ascertained from an agreement (up to the third decimal place) between two potential or resistance measurements. The equilibrium was further examined by allowing the nucleic acid solution to remain in contact with different amounts of NaOH (as used in potentiometric and conductometric titrations) in a series of Jena bottles for about 24 hours. The pH value of the content of each bottle was measured separately and compared with the corresponding data of actual titrations where readings were taken 15 to 20 minutes after addition of each instalment of the base (Table III).

TABLE III

*Yeast nucleic acid solution.*Conc. = 1.089 g./litre. Vol. taken = 10 c.c. Temp. = $35^{\circ} \pm 0.1$.

<i>N</i> -NaOH added.	pH (obs.) in bottles after 24 hours.	pH in actual titration after 15 min.	<i>N</i> -NaOH added.	pH (obs.) in bottles after 24 hrs.	pH in actual titration after 15 min.
17.7×10^{-4}	3.62	3.60	59.0×10^{-4}	7.15	7.17
29.5	4.40	4.40	79.6	9.10	9.13
44.8	5.75	5.80	103.8	10.22	10.20

Hydrogen-ion Activity.—Results for hydrogen-ion activity (a_H) for different concentrations of the acid suspension have been presented in Table IV,

TABLE IV

*Yeast nucleic acid suspension (A)*Temp. = $35^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$

Conc.*	pH.	Free acidity ($a_H \times 10^8 N$).	Total acidity ($c_H \times 10^8 N$).	a_H/c_H ratio (f).	Conc.*	pH.	Free acidity ($a_H \times 10^8 N$).	Total acidity ($c_H \times 10^8 N$).	a_H/c_H ratio (f).
0.08	4.30	0.60	2.82	0.199	1.00	3.25	5.92	31.50	0.188
0.15	3.81	0.94	4.73	0.199	1.20	3.16	7.00	37.80	0.185
0.20	3.76	1.25	6.80	0.200	1.40	3.11	7.55	44.10	0.178
0.28	3.70	1.79	8.82	0.202	1.60	3.06	8.25	50.40	0.164
0.40	3.59	2.58	12.60	0.208	1.80	3.05	8.70	56.62	0.154
0.60	3.50	3.08	15.75	0.196	2.00	3.00	9.00	63.00	0.143
0.80	3.45	4.87	25.20	0.192					

* Conc. expressed in g. per litre.

Activity of H-ions have been calculated from pH values and presented in columns 3 and 8. The variations of a_H with concentration have been shown in Fig. 1. The curve is steeper at lower concentrations but the slope decreases at a concentration of approximately 1.4 g. per litre. There is, however, no sharp break in the curve.

FIG. 1.
 *a_H -c curve.*FIG. 2.
Potentiometric titration curve.

In columns 4 and 9 of the table the total titratable acidity (c_H) as obtained by potentiometric titration of the acid with NaOH at different concentrations have been presented. A complete potentiometric titration curve at one concentration has been shown in Fig. 2. The end-points for the titrations were determined from the steep inflexions which were found to occur at pH varying from 7.1 to 7.5. It appears from the c_H values that they vary linearly with concentration. This means that the total acidity per 100 g. of the acid remains constant at all concentrations to a value of approximately 325 m.e per 100 g. of the acid.

The ratio of free to total acidity at different dilutions has been calculated and presented in columns 5 and 10 of Table IV. A graphical representation of these data appear in Fig. 3. The curve obviously shows a slight rise at low concentrations, followed by a steep drop at 0.4 g./litre. A second break in the

FIG. 3.

 $a_H/a_T - c$ curve.

FIG. 4.

 $\Lambda - \sqrt{c}$ curve.

curve is also evident at a higher concentration of 1.4 g./litre. The curve thus simulates, to a certain extent, those obtained by Lottermoser and Püschel (*loc. cit.*) in the case of Ag-ion activity in the Ag-salts of alkyl sulphonic acids and also those obtained by Lottermoser and Frotzcher (*Koll.-chem. Beih.*, 1937, 45, 303) for the Cl^- activity of different alkyl pyridinium chlorides. A rise (though small) in the curve at low concentrations was also observed by these authors for Ag-ions in the Ag-salts of alkyl sulphonic acids having 12 and 14 atoms of carbon in the chain and for Cl^- ions in the octadecylpyridinium chloride.

Specific and Equivalent Conductance.—Results for variation of conductance with concentration of the solution have been presented in Table V.

TABLE V

Conc.	$\sqrt{c}$	Sp. condy. (κ) $\times 10^4$ mho	Sp. cony. calc. from eq $\times 10^4$	Equip. condy. $\times 10^4$ in mho.	Conc.*	$\sqrt{c}$	Sp. condy. (κ) $\times 10^4$ mho.	Sp. condy calc. from eq $\times 10^4$	Equip. condy. $\times 10^4$ in mho.
0.25	0.50	1.25	0.70	5.0	1.00	1.00	3.60	2.87	3.55
0.40	0.63	1.80	1.03	4.61	1.20	1.09	4.15	2.80	3.60
0.50	0.71	2.20	1.23	4.40	1.40	1.18	4.70	2.74	3.35
0.80	0.77	2.25	1.40	4.10	1.60	1.34	5.55	3.48	3.10
0.70	0.84	2.73	1.60	3.90	2.00	1.40	6.00	3.00	3.00
0.80	0.80	3.10	1.84	3.85					

* Conc. expressed in g./litre.

Columns 3 and 7 show the variation of specific conductance (κ) with concentration. By drawing the $\kappa-c$ curve from these data (the curve not presented here) it becomes evident that there is no point of special interest and the run of the curve is of the type found with most of the common electrolytes.

Equivalent weight of this acid cannot be definitely ascertained because the total acidity has been found to vary with the nature of the base used for titrating this acid, although such variations have been quite small in comparison with some soil colloids (*e. g.* hydrogen clays) investigated in these laboratories (unpublished work).

Equivalent conductivity cannot therefore be calculated in this case. We can, however, define a quantity, viz, conductivity per gram of the acid (Λ) which is proportional to the equivalent conductivity.

$$\Lambda = \frac{\kappa \times 1000}{c}$$

where c stands for the number of grams of the acid per litre of the solution.

When these Λ values (columns 5 & 10, Table V) are plotted against $\sqrt{c}$, we should normally expect to get a straight line according to Onsager's relation,

$$\Lambda_c = \Lambda_\infty - k\sqrt{c}$$

where the terms have their usual significance and k is a constant giving the slope of the straight line. Graphical representation of Λ against $\sqrt{c}$ is shown in Fig. 4. The graph presents the following features :

(i) Beyond a certain concentration (0.49 g./l.) Λ appears to diminish more rapidly with $\sqrt{c}$. The curve thus presents a break in this region but the break is not so sharp as those obtained with many colloidal electrolytes by Hartley (*loc. cit.*), McBain (*loc. cit.*) and Lottermoser (*loc. cit.*).

(ii) Λ does not appear to pass through a minimum but shows a second break near about a concentration of 1.4 g./l. beyond which a slightly steeper run is observed.

(iii) The curve, extrapolated to zero concentration, gives low values for equivalent conductance. The value obtained by straight line extrapolation gives a value of Λ which is much lower than that obtained from the activity of hydrogen ions alone

(iv) Columns 4 and 8 of Table V give values of specific conductance as calculated from the a_H at the corresponding concentrations as determined by potentiometric measurement of pH . Calculations have been carried out on the assumption that the equivalent conductivity of H ions at 35° is 400 mho (*cf.* Glassstone, "Electrochemistry of Solutions", 1937, p. 72; Int. Crit. Tables, 1929, VI, 259) and that it is not influenced by presence of other ions in solution (*cf.* independent migration of ions). The calculated values, as will be evident from the table, are in all cases lower than the observed values and it is of interest to note that the discrepancy increases with increasing concentration. This aspect will be discussed in a subsequent section.

Cataphoretic Velocity.—Cataphoretic velocities at different concentrations are given in Table VI and graphically represented in Fig. 5.

TABLE VI
Yeast nucleic acid solution.

Conc (g./l.)	Temp = 30°.		Conc. (g./l.)	Temp = 30°.	
	c. v. for sol A.	c. v. for sol B.		c. v. for sol A.	c. v. for sol B.
0.25	1.6×10^{-4}	—	1.30	7.8×10^{-4}	6.95×10^{-4}
0.40	2.1	—	1.40	7.2	6.61
0.80	4.6	5.9×10^{-4}	1.60	6.7	6.05
0.90	5.3	6.81	1.80	6.2	5.68
1.00	6.0	7.22	2.00	5.6	5.22

It is evident that c. v. at first increases with concentration, passes through a maximum and then decreases a little slowly. It has been observed in this laboratory (Mukherjee, Chaudhury and Ghosh, *Trans. Nat. Inst. Sci. India*, 1935, 1, 47) that aggregation during coagulation is often associated with increase in cataphoretic velocity. This suggests that during the rise of cataphoretic velocity probably aggregation of the anions of nucleic acid takes place. Measurements in

FIG. 5.
C.V. - c curve.

FIG. 6.
c-c curves.

this case begin from a concentration of 0.25 g. of the acid per litre. Lower concentrations could not, however, be studied since in these cases the particles were not distinctly visible under the microscope. When, however, the concentration was raised, higher than 1 g. per litre, particles could be vividly seen and some of them were found to possess greater velocity than the others. The size of such particles, as far as could be judged under the microscope, appeared to be larger in some cases. To confirm this point further, another sample of the nucleic acid sol (sol B) was similarly studied for its cataphoretic velocity at different concentrations.

The only inference that could be drawn from these measurements is that probably there is some type of aggregate formation in the nucleic acid sols. But whether this process is a progressive one from low concentrations or whether it begins at any critical concentration and ends some where else, could not be ascertained defini

Extinction Coefficient.—Kruyt and co-workers (*Kolloid Z.*, 1936, 75, 318) observed that Beer's law holds good for gold and selenium sols. Any deviation from Beer's law has been suggested by them to be due to some kind of internal change taking place in the colloid. Various types of deviations from Beer's law have been observed by different workers and it is not *a priori* possible to predict from theoretical considerations only whether any deviation from Beer's law should be due to change in the total number of particles or due to some other secondary phenomena.

Extinction coefficient has been calculated from the relation,

$$\log e \frac{I_0}{I} = \epsilon c l$$

where ϵ stands for extinction coefficient per unit concentration, l for the stratum thickness of the absorption cell and c for the concentration of the acid in g. per litre. ϵ therefore in the present case refers to extinction coefficient per g. of the acid per litre of the solution. I_0 represents the intensity of the incident radiation and I , that after transmission through the solution. By making necessary transformations, the relation becomes

$$2.303 \log_{10} \frac{I_0}{I} = \epsilon c l$$

The value of $\log_{10} \frac{I_0}{I}$ is therefore a measure of ϵ at a constant concentration c and at constant value of l . In these experiments an absorption cell of 1 cm. in thickness was always used.

FIG 7.
Absorption curves at diff. temp.

Before undertaking the actual measurement Lambert's law was verified in this system as a check on experimental accuracy. Results were found satisfactory.

Next the wave-length of maximum absorption was determined. Results are shown in Fig. 7. The curves extend from a wave-length of 4500Å to 6500Å beyond which visibility was extremely reduced.

Since maximum extinction coefficient means a maximum of absorption, from the figure the region of maximum appears to vary with the concentration, the displacement being towards the high frequency side with increase in concentration. In subsequent measurements to examine the effect of concentration on ϵ , measurements were made at a wave-length of 4600Å only.

Fig. 6 (curve 1) presents the variation of ϵ with concentration. The curve passes through a minimum which occurs at a concentration of approximately 0.4 g. per litre. The results in themselves are difficult to interpret. An elucidation was, however, attempted by examining the change in extinction coefficient (ϵ) during slow coagulation. For this reason a small quantity of $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ was added to the solution of the acid and the change in extinction coefficient noted with time. The result is shown in Fig. 6 (curve 2) in which a concentration of 2 g./litre was used. The units chosen have been arbitrary in order to accommodate the curve in the same figure for purposes of comparison. The value of ϵ (as evident from the figure) decreases with time, passes through a minimum and then fluctuates about some mean value as inferred from the shape of the curve.

DISCUSSION

From the foregoing results it is evident that the $a_H/c_H - c$ and $\Lambda - \sqrt{c}$ curves both show two breaks at about the same concentrations viz. 0.4 g./litre and 1.4 g./litre. The $c. v. - c$ curve shows only one maximum at a concentration of about 1.4 g./litre. Moreover, the $\Lambda - \sqrt{c}$ and $c. v. - c$ curves show close resemblance with similar curves obtained in the cases of some typical colloidal electrolytes (Pauli and Valko, "Electrochemie der Kolloide", 1929; Hartley, *Kolloid Z.*, 1939, 88, 22; Lottermoser and Püschel, *ibid.*, 1933, 63, 175).

The a_H/c_H (Fig. 3) ratio, which serves as a measure of the free acidity per g. of the acid, has low values at all concentrations and possesses a tendency to decrease with increase in concentration at higher concentration regions. Hartley (*loc. cit.*) explained these low values of the activity coefficients of the counter-ions in solutions of long chain alkyl halides, which are well known colloidal electrolytes, undergoing aggregation in solution. He assumed that a part of the counter-ions remained associated with the micelles formed by aggregation and a part only could form the ion-atmosphere and calculated the effect of the latter by the application of Debye-Hückel's theory by taking into account the size of the micelles, the charge on their surface after making allowance for the diminution brought about by that part of the counter-ions which remained firmly held up with the micelle. In a particular case, his calculations show that for a definite concentration ($\Lambda/100$) if

the negatively charged long-chain alkyl ion remains as a single monomer having point dimension, the value of the activity coefficient comes up to 0.96 ; while if they aggregate into a micelle of $24\text{\AA}$ diameter with 25 units of effective charge on the surface (after making allowance for the diminution caused by firmly held counter ions) the values of the activity coefficient becomes approximately 0.25 and if, in the same case, the size of the micelle be neglected, the activity coefficient equals about 0.07. He also points out that the effect of increasing concentration would be a further reduction in the value of the activity coefficient.

The low values of α_{H}/c_{H} , as observed here, find an explanation in the light of these discussions if the existence of aggregate formation be assumed in this case as well. The nature of the $\Lambda - \sqrt{c}$ curve in a way lends support to this view and shows the concentration where the formation of aggregates assumes considerable proportion to be near about 0.4 g./litre.

The increase of cataphoretic velocity with concentration should indicate an increase in the equivalent conductance of the micelle. Hartley reports a rise of equivalent conductance of the micelle ion in the aqueous solution of cetyl pyridinium bromide and McBain (*vide* Pauli and Valko, "Electrochemie der Kolloide", 1929, p. 584) reports a rise of transport number of the anions of many Na-soaps to values above unity. According to these workers this phenomenon has to be attributed to the aggregation of paraffin chain ions to form micelles. In the present system, since an increase in c. v. is evident from low concentrations (even below 0.40g./litre, where the $\Lambda - \sqrt{c}$ curve exhibits its first break), a progressive aggregate formation from very low concentrations appears to be likely.

In the case of nucleic acid solutions therefore, the critical concentrations, as indicated by the kinks in the $\Lambda - \sqrt{c}$ curve, lose much of their significance if aggregate formation be assumed to start below these concentrations. In this the first break in the $\Lambda - \sqrt{c}$ curve agrees with the first break in the $\alpha_{H}/c_{H} - c$ curve and therefore, from this point upwards the amount of active hydrogen ions per g. of the acid begins to decrease with concentration. This may be due to the arrest of more and more hydrogen ions in the double layer surrounding each micelle. A persistent increase in c. v. at this region and much further beyond this point, may probably be due to a marked increase in the size and charge density of the anion at low concentrations than at higher ones where the micelles acquire higher charge and bigger size so that the common effect of the change of concentration becomes evident.

An increase of c. v. and hence the equivalent conductance of the anion will necessarily indicate a very low value for the ionic conductance of the oppositely charged ion (*cf.* Hartley, *loc. cit.*). So there is little justification for calculation of specific conductivity of the acid from H-ion activity alone, as given in Table V, on the basis of a constant value of the ionic conductance of hydrogen ion equal to that at infinite dilutions. The progress of aggregate formation will arrest more and more

hydrogen ions in the double layer and will reduce its mobility and the effect is expected to be more prominent with increase in concentration. A correction for decrease in mobility of hydrogen ions will decrease the calculated value of specific conductivity and will tend to further increase the discrepancy between the calculated and observed values. A discrepancy between the observed and calculated values of sp. conductivity is, however, not very clear up till now.

The nature of the ϵ - c curve and a comparison of this with that obtained by the addition of $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ into the system also serves to indicate the occurrence of aggregate formation in this case with increase in concentration. That the addition of $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ serves to increase the size of the particles has also been confirmed by turbidity measurements (data to be presented in a subsequent communication).

To sum up, the evidences obtained in course of these investigations go to indicate the existence of aggregate formation which probably proceeds from very low concentrations and appears to be progressive at higher concentration regions.

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